

Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction and Their Impact on Customer Loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy

Muhamad Fattah Mahdi¹
Faculty Economics and Bussiness
Universitas Mercu Buana
Jakarta, Indonesia

Ririn Wulandari²
Faculty of Economis and Bussiness
Universitas Mercu Buana
Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The aim of the study was to analyze the factors that affect customer satisfaction and their impact on customer loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy in the Jabodetabek area. Researchers used Partial Least Square (PLS) as a technique to analyze the measurement and structural. The type of research is descriptive quantitative with direct survey method involving 135 Google Form respondents.

The results of this study indicate that all four variables, such as price perception, brand image, brand trust, and e-service quality have a direct positive and significant influence on customer loyalty. Brand image has a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction, while price perception, brand trust, and E-service quality have no effect on customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction has a direct positive and significant effects on customer loyalty. The results of the indirect test show that all independent variables (X) through mediation (Z) have a positive and significant influence on the dependent variable (Y). The implications of this research for the Kimia Farma Pharmacy in the Jabodetabek area are to increase price affordability, pay attention to consumer trust, and improve the quality of Kimia Farma Mobile services, as these variables will have an impact on customer loyalty.

Keywords:- Price Perception, Brand Image, Brand Trust, E-Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty.

I. INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction is one of the dominant determinants influencing customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction is the dominant factor influencing customer loyalty (Dimiyati, 2017). Decrease in satisfaction can impact on a decrease in customer loyalty. Customer loyalty is largely determined by customer satisfaction with the products and services provided by product and service providers. If the customer is satisfied, his loyalty will automatically increase, while if customer satisfaction decreases, then customer loyalty will also decrease. Improvement of customer loyalty can be started from improving customer satisfaction, where customer satisfaction itself is determined by many factors which are marketing mix factors such as price, brand

image, brand trust, service quality, and many other marketing mix factors.

The results of a survey conducted by lifepal on the Yahoo finance website show that Kimia Farma is a pharmaceutical company that has a performance above the JCI. However, when viewed from the company's profit, it turns out that in that year Kimia Farma actually experienced a decrease in net profit. According to the results of an interview with Wisnu Sucahyo (General Manager of Kimia Farma Business Development on 15 October 2021), the pandemic and the large-scale social restriction (PSBB) policy have caused a significant decline in people's purchasing power. In addition to these phenomena, in the pre-observation of 30 customers of Kimia Farma's pharmacies, the results of the analysis showed that most of the respondents chose to buy drugs at Kimia Farma's pharmacies because (1) Guaranteed drug quality (26.7%), (2) Can order drugs online (23.3%).

A decrease in the number of visitors is synonymous with a decrease in customer loyalty. Kotler and Keller (2013) revealed that customer loyalty is a promise of customers who survive every day to make consistent and continuous product purchases in the future, even though marketing efforts have the opportunity to change customer behavior. The decline in loyalty needs to be stopped so that Kimia Farma Lagi's performance will increase, thus it is necessary to conduct research to identify the influencing factors by testing the previous findings.

Based on the description above, a phenomenon is obtained that the Kimia Farma Pharmacy, which has a fairly large brand, is experiencing problems with decreasing the number of visitors since the Covid-19 pandemic, while other brands still have maximum profits both during the pandemic and after the Covid-19 pandemic. Based on existing phenomena and supported by previous GAP research, the title of this study is "Factors that influence customer satisfaction and their impact on Customer Loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy".

II. LITERATURE

A. Customer Satisfaction

Kotler (2002) reveals that customer satisfaction is a consideration that comes when comparing the performance of products/services that are in mind with the expected performance. Furthermore, Bitner and Zeithaml (2003) stated that customer satisfaction is an assessment given by consumers regarding products or services, whether they have fulfilled the needs and expectations of customers or not. As for Hansemark and Albinsson (2004) revealed that customer satisfaction is generally a behavior or emotional response that directs the difference between what the customer wants and what the customer gets. Irawan (2004) revealed that the factors that influence customer satisfaction, including price (perceived price), service quality (quality of service), product quality (quality of products), emotional factors and efficiency (convenience).

B. Customer Loyalty

Ishaq (in Jeremia and Djurwati, 2019) reveals that loyalty is a series of actions, where satisfaction has an influence on perceived quality. This means that satisfaction can have a strong influence on customer loyalty and behavior. Oliver (in Jeremia and Djurwati, 2019) states that customer loyalty is a loyal promise for consumers to buy or prioritize a product continuously and repeatedly. This has a positive impact in the form of continuous purchases of the same brand, even though these consumers are situationally deceived by competitors to exchange and buy other brands. Furthermore, Rizki Zulfikar (2008) revealed that customer loyalty is characterized by a strong belief that tends to remain and for a long time towards a product owned by the store/company that is the choice and there is no effort to switch to other products, even contributing in influencing other consumers to participate in using the product.

C. Price Perception

Kotler and Armstrong (2012) revealed that the perception of price is a bill of a good or service. More broadly, Kotler and Armstrong revealed that the perception of price is the total number of valuations submitted by regular consumers as a form of business to benefit from using an item or service. Andi (2015) reveals that price perception is the main factor that influences a buyer's decision and has a major role in deciding to purchase goods or services. Therefore, before determining the perceived price, the company should look for a reference price perception of a product first.

D. Brand Image

Keller (2013) revealed that brand image is a comment or view from product users on a brand based on the strengths and weaknesses of the brand. Brand Image is a belief that is embodied in the minds of customers about the object or product they use. Furthermore, Kotler and Keller (2012) explained that brand image is the response and trust of product users, as manifested in the minds of consumers. A good brand image can provide advantages for banks, including realizing competitive advantage. Brand image can be interpreted as a product user's perception or view of a

brand that is realized according to the information obtained by the product user through the consumer's experience when using the product or service.

E. Brand Trust

Warusman and Untarini (2016) state that brand trust is a valuation that arises from several things that can bring pleasure to product users. That is, each product user relates brand trust with experience in using the brand. Meanwhile, Delgado Ballester and Menuera (in Rahmawati and Sunaji, 2015) stated that brand trust is the capability of a brand to be trusted based on the trust of product users that the product or service can meet the valuation that has been determined based on the trust of product users that the brand can meet customer needs. Rahayu and Harsono (2017) stated that brand trust provides a valuation that can continuously increase purchases. This can happen if product users are loyal to the brand they use and recommend it to other parties.

F. E-service Quality

Zehir and Narcikara (2016) revealed, e-service quality is an effort to use products facilitated by the latest technology. Furthermore, Kurt and Atrek (2012) stated that electronic-based services can accommodate product purchases effectively and efficiently. Thus, service levels are increasingly believed to be a key part of electronic commerce. Online services are technically more effective and efficient than traditional services. Therefore, service quality is a determining tool for success in electronic sales (Zehir and Narcikara, 2016)

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Referring to the background and literature review above, the framework in this study can be developed as shown in Figure 2 below.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Based on Figure 2 above, there are a number of hypotheses that emerge in this study, namely as follows.

- H1: Perceived price influences customer loyalty
- H2: Brand image has an effect on customer loyalty
- H3: Brand trust has an effect on customer loyalty
- H4: E-service quality affects customer loyalty
- H5: Perceived price has an effect on customer satisfaction

- H6: Brand Image has an effect on customer satisfaction
- H7: Brand trust has an effect on customer satisfaction
- H8: E-service quality affects customer satisfaction
- H9: Customer satisfaction affects customer loyalty
- H10: Perceived price through customer satisfaction has an effect on customer loyalty
- H11: Brand Image through customer satisfaction influences customer loyalty
- H12: Brand trust through customer satisfaction influences customer loyalty
- H13: E-service quality through customer satisfaction influences customer loyalty

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

Quantitative method with explanatory survey used in this research. The author uses a questionnaire given to Kimia

Farma Pharmacy visitors who purchase products after being in the Greater Jakarta area as data collection. The author uses 135 valid respondents for analysis. Data were analyzed descriptively through several stages, namely the distribution of questionnaires, the descriptive analysis stage of respondent characteristics, the variable descriptive analysis stage. In this study, PLS SEM analysis was used to test the hypothesis.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This research involved 135 respondents who were all customers of Kimia Farma pharmacies in the Greater Jakarta area. Based on the results of data collection, the following is a description of the characteristics of the respondents which can be observed in Table 1:

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

			F	%
1	Gender		135	
		Laki-laki	94	69,63%
		Perempuan	41	30,37%
2	Age		135	
		<25 years	3	2,22%
		25-35 years	42	31,11%
		35-45 years	75	55,56%
		>55 years	15	11,11%
3	Education		135	
		SD-SMA	11	8,15%
		Diploma	26	19,26%
		S1	87	64,44%
		S2/S3	11	8,15%
4	Frequency of Purchases at Kimia Farma Pharmacy		135	
		1 time	14	10,37%
		1-5 times	51	37,78%
		>5 times	70	51,85%
5	Experience using the Kimia Farma application		135	
		ever	8	5,93%
		never	127	94,07%

Based on the table above, the results of the analysis of the sex of the respondents showed that the majority of Kimia Farma Pharmacy respondents were male (69.63%) and as many as 30.37% of respondents were female. The age range of the respondents was mostly 35-45 years (55.56%), 31.11% of respondents were 25-35 years old, 2.22% were <25 years old and 11.11% were > 55 years old. The education of the most dominant respondents was at the undergraduate level (64.44%), while the rest were elementary-high school education (8.15%), diploma (19.26%) and as many as 8.15% of respondents had master's/doctoral degrees. The frequency of purchases of respondents at the Kimia Farma Pharmacy, as much as > 5 times (51.85%), while 10.37% of respondents had bought drugs at the Kimia Farma pharmacy 1 time and as many as 37, 78% of respondents have bought drugs at the

Kimia Farma Pharmacy 1-5 times. Experience of respondents using the Kimia Farma application 94.07% of respondents had never used the Kimia Farma online application, while the remaining 5.93% of respondents had used the Kimia Farma online application.

This research model contains 6 variables, namely price perception computation, brand image, brand trust, e-service quality, and customer loyalty. All these variables are 1st order latent constructs which are known through several standards. The price perception construct is a 1st order construct consisting of 4 (four) measurement standards, the brand image construct is a 1st order construct with 6 measurement standards, the brand trust construct is a 1st order construct with 6 measurement standards, measurement,

the e-service quality construct is a construct 1st order with 5 measurement standards, the customer loyalty construct is the 1st order construct with 5 measurement standards and the customer loyalty variable is the 1st order construct with 2 measurement indicators. Referring to these operations.

Fig 2: SEM Model Specifications PLS

The diagram in Figure 2 above describes the relationships between constructs indicated by arrows. The arrows indicate that there is a direct causal relationship between the constructs.

Table 2. Composite Reliability

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Price perception (X1)	0.819	0.880	Reliable
Brand Image (X2)	0.904	0.926	Reliable
Brand trust (X3)	0.897	0.921	Reliable
E-service	0.915	0.940	Reliable

quality (X4)			
Customer loyalty (Y)	0.907	0.931	Reliable
Customer satisfaction (Z)	0.911	0.957	Reliable

Data from Table 2 shows that the composite reliability and cronbachs alpha valuations of all constructs are more than 0.7. This illustrates that all constructs meet the required reliability.

Table 3. AVE Value Test Results

Variable	Condition	AVE
Price perception (X1)	>0.5	0.649
Brand Image(X2)	>0.5	0.678
Brand trust(X3)	>0.5	0.662
E-service quality(X4)	>0.5	0.798
Customer loyalty (Y)	>0.5	0.732
Customer satisfaction (Z)	>0.5	0.918

All the constructs in Table 3 describe an AVE valuation that is greater than 0.50, with the smallest valuation being 0.649 for the perceived price variable (X1) and the largest being 0.798 for the E-service quality variable (X4). The valuation presented has met the requirements for the minimum AVE value limit that has been set, which is 0.50.

Table 4. R-Square Test Results

Variable	R Square
Y	0.842
Z	0.695

Based on the R2 value in the table above, it indicates that the variable price perception (X1), brand image (X2), brand trust (X3), e-service quality (X4), and customer satisfaction (Z) can describe the variability of customer loyalty constructs (Y) of 84.2% and the price perception variable (X1), brand image (X2), brand trust (X3), e-service quality (X4) can describe the customer satisfaction variable (Z).

Table 5. Results of the Direct Effect Test

	Hipotesis	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Hasil
H-1	X1 -> Y	0.161	2.034	0.043	Accepted
H-2	X2 -> Y	0.390	4.609	0.000	Accepted
H-3	X3 -> Y	0.248	2.529	0.012	Accepted
H-4	X4 -> Y	0.202	3.743	0.000	Accepted
H-5	X1 -> Z	0.050	0.401	0.689	Rejected
H-6	X2 -> Z	0.477	3.237	0.001	Accepted
H-7	X3 -> Z	-0.088	0.590	0.555	Rejected
H-8	X4 -> Z	0.100	1.525	0.128	Rejected
H-9	Z -> Y	0.347	2.415	0.016	Accepted

According to the test results, it is understood that price perception (X1) is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty (Y), indicated by sig. = 0.043 <0.05, T statistic 2.034 > 1.96 and a positive path coefficient of 0.161 so that it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted. Brand Image (X2) has a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty (Y), indicated by sig. = 0.000 <0.05, T statistic 4.609 > 1.96 and a positive path coefficient of 0.390 so it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted.

Furthermore, brand trust (X3) has a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty (Y), indicated by sig. = 0.012 <0.05, T statistic 2.529 > 1.96 and a positive path coefficient of 0.248 so that it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted. E-service quality (X4) has a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty (Y), indicated by sig. = 0.000 <0.05, T statistic 3.743 > 1.96 and a positive path coefficient of 0.202 so that it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

Price perception (X1) has no impact on customer satisfaction (Z) marked by sig. = 0.689 > 0.05 and T statistic 0.401 < 1.96. Therefore, it is understandable that the fifth hypothesis is rejected. Brand image (X2) has a significant and positive effect on customer satisfaction (Z), indicated by sig. = 0.001 <0.05, T statistic 3.237 > 1.96 and a positive path coefficient of 0.477 so that it can be concluded that the sixth hypothesis is accepted.

Brands trust (X3) has no effect on customer satisfaction (Z) indicated by sig. = 0.555 > 0.05 and T statistic 0.590 <1.96 so it can be drawn that the seventh hypothesis is rejected. E-service quality (X4) has no effect on customer satisfaction (Z) marked by sig. = 0.128 > 0.05 and T statistic 1.525 < 1.96 so it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis is rejected. Customer satisfaction (Z) has a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty (Y), indicated by sig. = 0.016 <0.05, T statistic 2.415 > 1.96 and a positive path coefficient of 0.347 so that it can be concluded that the ninth hypothesis is accepted.

Table 6. Uji Pengaruh Tidak Langsung

	hypothesis	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Results
H-10	X1 -> Y -> Z	0.056	1.621	0.015	Accepted
H-11	X2 -> Y -> Z	0.136	1.958	0.034	Accepted
H-12	X3 -> Y -> Z	0.086	1.770	0.011	Accepted
H-13	X4 -> Y -> Z	0.070	2.012	0.045	Accepted

Table 6 describes that the perception of price (X1) on customer loyalty (Y) through customer satisfaction (Z) has a p value of 0.015 with a T statistic of 1.621 with a positive indirect path coefficient of 0.056. Thus, it can be understood that customer satisfaction (Z) can mediate price perceptions (X1) on customer loyalty (Y) so that the tenth hypothesis is accepted.

Brand image (X2) on customer loyalty (Y) through customer satisfaction (Z) gets a p value of 0.034 with a T statistic of 1.952 with a positive indirect path coefficient of 0.136. Therefore, it can be understood that customer satisfaction (Z) can mediate brand image (X2) on customer loyalty (Y) so that the eleventh hypothesis is accepted.

Brands trust (X3) on customer loyalty (Y) through customer satisfaction (Z) gets a p value of 0.011 with a T statistic of 1.770 with a positive indirect path coefficient of 0.086. Therefore, it can be drawn that customer satisfaction (Z) can mediate brand trust (X3) on customer loyalty (Y) so that the twelfth hypothesis is accepted.

E-service quality (X4) on customer loyalty (Y) through customer satisfaction (Z) gets a p value of 0.045 with a T statistic of 2.012 with a positive indirect path coefficient of 0.070. Therefore, it can be drawn that customer satisfaction (Z) can mediate e-service quality (X4) on customer loyalty (Y) so that the thirteenth hypothesis is accepted.

Price perception indicators consist of price commensurate with product quality, price commensurate with benefits, price competitiveness, and price affordability. This is in line with the statement of respondents who revealed that the indicators on price perceptions belong to the high or good category. Referring to the research results that have been presented, the efforts that have been made by Kimia Farma Pharmacy to increase customer loyalty are to pay close attention to price issues, because price affordability is a crucial comparison aspect for consumers. If the price of a product is more affordable than the price of the same product elsewhere, customers will choose and use the product and customer loyalty will emerge. So therefore,

Brand image significant and positive impact on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the t-value of 4.609 which is greater than 1.96. The higher the brand image, the higher the level of customer loyalty. Vice versa. Behavior towards a particular brand often also has an impact on customer loyalty. The positive views and beliefs of product users towards a particular brand can shape buying interest and can increase consumer loyalty. This is in line with what was conveyed by Rangkuti (2002) which revealed that the views of product users towards certain brands are physically different from their views of other brands. The image of a brand will always be linked in order to form loyalty to a particular brand. This is known as brand loyalty.

Brand trust significant impact on customer loyalty. The results of the SEM-PLS test indicate that the brand trust variable is significant and has a positive impact on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the t-value of 2.529 which is greater than 1.96. The higher the brand trust, the higher the level of customer loyalty. Vice versa. Product users who always buy continuously and give their full trust can show their loyalty to the brand. Therefore, the research results show that brand trust and loyalty have a strong relationship. E-service quality can affect customer loyalty. The results of the SEM-PLS test illustrate that the e-service quality variable is significant and has a positive impact on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the t-value of 3.743 which has a higher number than 1.96. The higher the e-service quality, the higher the level of customer loyalty. Vice versa. Customers who are satisfied with the e-service quality of Kimia Farma Pharmacy can recommend Kimia Farma Pharmacy to others so that customer loyalty is formed. The tests carried out in this study are consistent with those carried out by Lin et al. (2016) who revealed that e-service quality has a significant effect on customer loyalty.

Perceived price does not affect customer satisfaction. The results of the SEM-PLS test show that the t-value is 0.401 which is smaller than 1.96. The higher or lower the perceived price does not affect customer satisfaction. Therefore, the results of the research data test were not in line with the results of tests carried out by (Kudus et al., 2020); (Riadi et al., 2021); (Purwoko & Haryana, 2021); (Ronasih & Widhiastuti, 2021); (Darmanto & Ariyanti, 2020); (Anggraini & Budiarti, 2020); (Santoso, 2019) (KAGK Putra & Seminary, 2020) and (R. Putra, 2021) which reveal that price perceptions affect customer satisfaction.

Brand image have an impact on customer satisfaction. The SEM-PLS test illustrates that Brand Image variables are significant and have a positive impact on customer satisfaction. This can be observed from the t-value of 3.237 which is greater than 1.96. The higher the brand image, the higher the level of customer satisfaction. Vice versa. A good brand image will increase customer and prospective customer satisfaction and be more trusted or provide more satisfaction for customers. These results are in line with those conducted by Prasetya & Yulius' research (2018); Diab (2009); Noor et al. (2020); Caroline & Karina (2018); Rafdinal et al. (2021); Nurfadila et al. (2015); Samuel & Lianto (2017). The results of this study illustrate that brand image is proven to be a determining aspect that can affect customer satisfaction.

*Brand trust*mo impact on customer satisfaction. The results of the SEM-PLS test showed a t-value of 0.590 which was less than 1.96. The higher or lower the brand trust, it does not affect customer satisfaction. This is not in line with research conducted by research conducted by Noegroho et al. (2013); Herliza & Saputri (2016); Widagdo & Yanuar (2021); Marsellina & Budiono (2019); Dharmayana & Rahanatha (2017); Suryani & Rosalina (2019); Lailiyah (2020); and Suryani & Rosalina (2019) which show results

that a decrease in brand trust can impact on a decrease in customer satisfaction.

E-service quality no impact on customer satisfaction. The results of the SEM-PLS test show that the E-service quality variable has no effect on customer satisfaction. This can be seen from the t-value of 1.525 which is smaller than 1.96. The higher or lower the E-service quality, it has no effect on customer satisfaction. The results of this study are not in line with research conducted by research by Pasa et al. (2020); Ramadan et al. (2021); Nurmanah & Nugroho (2021); and Zulfa et al. (2019) showed the results that E-service quality greatly influences customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction has an impact on customer loyalty. The SEM-PLS test indicates that the customer satisfaction variable is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the t-value of 2.415 which is greater than 1.96. The higher the customer satisfaction, the higher the level of customer loyalty. Vice versa. Customer satisfaction is the main factor that influences customer loyalty. Declining customer satisfaction can have an impact on decreasing the level of customer loyalty because customer loyalty is determined by customer satisfaction with the products offered. If customers get satisfaction from these products, it can be ascertained that customer loyalty will increase. Meanwhile, if customer satisfaction decreases, then customer loyalty may also decrease. Dimiyati (2017); Devindiani & Wibowo (2016); Suryawan & Sharif (2018); And Hadiwidjaja & Dharmayanti (2014) which reveals that customer satisfaction affects customer loyalty.

Customer satisfaction has an impact on customer loyalty. The SEM-PLS test describes the price perception variable through customer satisfaction as having a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the sig value of 0.015 <0.05. The higher the price perception can increase customer satisfaction and loyalty. Vice versa. Perceived price is the main factor that can influence the choice of product users. Price perception also plays a role in deciding product purchases. Therefore, the company should look for some references to the price perception of a product that is considered high enough in sales first. When product users have a price perception that is in accordance with the valuation they get, then consumer loyalty can increase. The increase in product user loyalty has implications for brand loyalty. This research is in line with research conducted by Putra (2021); Santoso (2019); Anggraini & Budiarti (2020); Purwoko & Haryana (2021) which shows that price perceptions can affect the level of consumer satisfaction, and this can have implications for the level of consumer loyalty.

Brand image through customer satisfaction effect on customer loyalty. The SEM-PLS test shows that the brand image variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive impact on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the sig. 0.034 <0.05. The higher the brand image, the customer satisfaction and customer loyalty can increase.

Vice versa. Brand image plays an important role for the company. Brand image can be said as a positive impression that is instilled in the minds of product users. Product users can evaluate brands based on positive impressions in their fields, such as product reputation, product superiority, and easily recognizable products (Prasetya & Yulius, 2018; Diab, 2009; Noor et al., 2020; Caroline & Karina, 2018; Rafdinal et al., 2021; Nurfadila et al., 2015; Semuel & Lianto, 2017). Consumer loyalty can be determined based on the position of the brand image for product users. The better the brand image, the consumer loyalty can be sure to increase. A high level of consumer satisfaction can affect the level of consumer loyalty (Dimiyati, 2017; Devindiani & Wibowo, 2016; Suryawan & Sharif, 2018; Hadiwidjaja & Dharmayanti, 2014).

Brand trust through customer satisfaction has an influence on customer loyalty. The SEM-PLS test shows that the brand trust variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive impact on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the sig. $0.011 < 0.05$. The higher the brand trust, the higher the customer satisfaction and loyalty. Vice versa. Brand trust given by product users can increase purchases continuously. This can happen if consumers are loyal to the brand they consume and recommend it to people (Rahayu and Harsono, 2017). The higher it is the level of brand trust assessed by consumers, it will grow the level of consumer loyalty to a product or service. Conversely, when consumers value brand trust low, the level of customer loyalty is low (Noegroho et al., 2013; Herliza & Saputri, 2016; Widagdo & Yanuar, 2021; Marsellina & Budiono, 2019; Dharmayana & Rahanatha, 2017). The level of consumers determined by the level of brand trust can have implications for the level of consumer loyalty to a product or service (Dimiyati, 2017; Devindiani & Wibowo, 2016; Suryawan & Sharif, 2018; Hadiwidjaja & Dharmayanti, 2014). In other words, brand trust affects customer loyalty and has implications for customer loyalty.

E-service quality through customer satisfaction effect on customer loyalty. The results of the SEM-PLS test show that the e-service quality variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive impact on customer loyalty. This can be seen from the sig. $0.045 < 0.05$. The higher the e-service quality, the higher the customer satisfaction and loyalty. Vice versa, the lower the e-service quality, the lower customer satisfaction and loyalty. E-service quality is a requirement for customers who are getting used to making purchase transactions supported by information technology in many services, including services for purchasing medicines. The better the e-services provided, the higher customer loyalty will be. However, when the online service is felt to be not good, then it can make low customer loyalty to the service (Pasa et al., 2020; Ramadan et al., 2021; Nurmanah & Nugroho, 2021; Zulfa et al., 2019). This shows that E-service quality has an important role in forming customer loyalty. With a high level of loyalty due to good E-service quality, it can increase customer loyalty (Dimiyati, 2017; Devindiani & Wibowo, 2016; Suryawan & Sharif, 2018; Hadiwidjaja & Dharmayanti, 2014). In other

words, E-service quality through customer satisfaction can affect customer loyalty. This shows that E-service quality has an important role in forming customer loyalty. With a high level of loyalty due to good E-service quality, it can increase customer loyalty (Dimiyati, 2017; Devindiani & Wibowo, 2016; Suryawan & Sharif, 2018; Hadiwidjaja & Dharmayanti, 2014). In other words, E-service quality through customer satisfaction can affect customer loyalty.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

- Based on the hypothesis test on the price perception variable, price perception is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy.
- Based on hypothesis testing on the brand image variable, brand image is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on hypothesis testing on the brand trust variable, brand trust is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on the hypothesis test on the variable e-service quality, e-service quality has a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on the hypothesis test on the price perception variable, price perceptions have no effect on customer satisfaction at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on hypothesis testing on the brand image variable, brand image is significant and has a positive effect on customer satisfaction at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on hypothesis testing on the brand trust variable, brand trust has no effect on customer satisfaction at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on the hypothesis test on the variable e-service quality, e-service quality has no effect on customer satisfaction at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on hypothesis testing on customer satisfaction variables, customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy
- Based on the hypothesis test, the price perception variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty
- Based on the hypothesis test, the brand image variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty
- Based on the hypothesis test, the brand trust variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty
- Based on the hypothesis test, the e-service quality variable through customer satisfaction is significant and has a positive effect on customer loyalty.

Kimia Farma Pharmacy needs to pay attention to the prices of the products it sells. This is because the data test illustrates that customer perceptions regarding drug prices at Kimia Farma Pharmacy affect customer satisfaction and loyalty at Kimia Farma Pharmacy. In addition to price, consumer trust also needs to be considered because consumer trust is one of the aspects that influence customer satisfaction and has an impact on customer loyalty. Kimia Farma Mobile services also need to be considered because it turns out that there are quite a lot of Kimia Farma mobile service users where this application is assessed.

In subsequent studies, the authors suggest adding more variables, especially those that have not been studied and have an impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty, such as service quality and product quality.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Susanto, T. W. P., Sudapet, I. N., Subagyo, H. D., & Suyono, J. (2021). The Effect Of Service Quality And Price On Customer Satisfaction And Repurchase Intention (Case Study At Crown Prince Hotel Surabaya). *Quantitative Economics And Management Studies*, 2(5). <https://doi.org/10.35877/454ri.Qems325>
- [2]. Noor, F., Utari, W., & Mardi W., N. (2020). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Persepsi Harga Citra *Brand* Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Serta Dampaknya Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen (Studi Pada Konsumen Produk Pt. Salim Ivomas Pratama Kecamatan Bojonegoro Kabupaten Bojonegoro). *Jurnal Mitra Manajemen*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.52160/Ejmm.V4i4.374>
- [3]. Nurfadila, N., Sutomo, M., & Asriadi, A. (2015). Pengaruh Citra *Brand* Dan Kepercayaan *Brand* Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Serta Dampaknya Terhadap Loyalitas *Brand* Sepeda Motor *Brand* Honda. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Universitas Tadulako (Jimut)*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.22487/Jimut.V1i3.33>
- [4]. Nurmanah, I., & Nugroho, E. S. (2021). Pengaruh Kepercayaan (*Trust*) Dan Kualitas Pelayanan Online (*E-service quality*) Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Online Shop Bukalapak. *At-Tadbir: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.31602/Atd.V5i1.3384>
- [5]. Pasa, E. G., Wulandari, J., & Adistya, D. (2020). Analisis *E-Trust*, *E-Wom* Dan *E-service quality* Dalam Keputusan Pembelian Online. *Jurnal Perspektif Bisnis*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.23960/Jpb.V3i2.19>
- [6]. Prasetya, W., & Yulius, C. (2018). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk Dan Citra *Brand* Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Dan Minat Beli Ulang: Studi Pada Produk Eatlah. *Jurnal Teknologi*, 11(2).
- [7]. Purwoko, S., & Haryana, A. (2021). Pengaruh Kemasan, Kualitas Dan Persepsi Harga Produk Susu Terhadap Kepuasan Dan Loyalitas Pelanggan Pt. Dwimitra Usaha Global. *Jurnal Administrasi Dan Manajemen*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.52643/Jam.V10i2.1130>
- [8]. Putra, K. A. G. K., & Seminari, N. K. (2020). Kualitas Produk, Kualitas Layanan, Dan Kewajaran Persepsi Harga Berpengaruh Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan The Old Champ Cafe. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 9(10). <https://doi.org/10.24843/Ejmunud.2020.V09.I10.P01>
- [9]. Putra, R. (2021). Determinasi Kepuasan Pelanggan Dan Loyalitas Pelanggan Terhadap Kualitas Produk, Citra *Brand* Dan Persepsi Harga (Literature Review Manajemen Pemasaran). *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Sistem Informasi*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.31933/Jemsi.V2i4.461>
- [10]. Rafdinal, W., Putri, Y., & Ridhaningsih, F. (2021). Model Loyalitas *Brand* Pada Teh Kemasan Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Riset Bisnis Dan Investasi*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.35313/Jrbi.V6i2.1923>
- [11]. Ramadan, F., Muchtar, & Hafid, H. (2021). Pengaruh Online Customer Review Dan *E-service quality* Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Melalui Marketplace. *Jurnal Forum Ekonomi*, 23(3).
- [12]. Riadi, M., Kamase, J., & Mapparenta, M. (2021). Pengaruh Persepsi Harga, Promosi Dan Kualitas Layanan Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Mobil Toyota (Studi Kasus Pada Pt. Hadji Kalla Cabang Alauddin). *Journal Of Management Science (Jms)*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.52103/Jms.V2i1.320>
- [13]. Ronasih, M. Y., & Widhiastuti, H. (2021). Kualitas Pelayanan, Faktor Emosional Dan Persepsi Harga Terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen Melalui Kepuasan Konsumen. *Philanthropy: Journal Of Psychology*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.26623/Philanthropy.V5i1.3303>
- [14]. Santoso, J. B. (2019). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Kualitas Pelayanan, Dan Persepsi Harga Terhadap Kepuasan Dan Loyalitas Konsumen. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 16(01). <https://doi.org/10.36406/Jam.V16i01.271>
- [15]. Samuel, H., & Lianto, A. S. (2017). Analisis Ewom, *Brand Image*, *Brand Trust* Dan Minat Beli Produk Smartphone Di Surabaya. *Interkomunika*, 2(2).
- [16]. Suryani, S., & Rosalina, S. S. (2019). Pengaruh *Brand Image*, *Brand Trust*, Dan Kualitas Layanan Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Ulang Dengan Kepuasan Konsumen Sebagai Variabel Moderating (Studi Pada Startup Business Unicorn Indonesia). *Journal Of Business Studies*, 04(1).
- [17]. Suryawan, I. Kadek Wawan, & Sharif, O. Omar. (2018). Pengaruh Kualitas Llayanan Penerbangan Terhadap Kepuasan Penumpang Dan Loyalitas (Studi Kasus : Penerbangan Garuda Indonesia). *Jurnal Wacana Ekonomi*, 17(03).
- [18]. Widagdo, A. B., & Yanuar, Y. (2021). Analisis Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Word Of Mouth Ayam Geprek Don. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan*, 5(3). <https://doi.org/10.24912/Jmbk.V5i3.11867>

- [19]. Zulfa, L., Hidayati, R., Tinggi, S., Ekonomi, I., Surakarta, A. A. S., Tinggi, S., Ekonomi, I., Surakarta, A. A. S., Hasan, A., Mewoh, F. M., Tampi, J. R. E., Mukuan, D. D. S., Anggreani, M. P., & Baihaqi, M. (2019). Analisis Pengaruh Persepsi Risiko, Kualitas Situs Web, Pembelian Konsumen E-Commerce Shopee Di Kota Semarang. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen*, 4(3).
- [20]. Kudus, N. R., Nasrul, N., & Juharsah, J. (2020). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Persepsi Harga Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Pengguna Jasa Transportasi Online Grab-Car Di Kota Kendari. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Kewirausahaan*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.55598/jmk.v12i2.14022>
- [21]. Lailiyah, N. (2020). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Kepercayaan *Brand* Terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen Dengan Kepuasan Konsumen Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Hijab Medyna Colletion Situs Shop Online. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen (Jimmu)*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.33474/jimmu.v5i1.3889>
- [22]. Marsellina, M., & Budiono, H. (2019). Pengaruh Kepercayaan *Brand* Dan Citra *Brand* Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Uniqlo Di Jakarta. *Jurnal Manajerial Dan Kewirausahaan*, 1(4). <https://doi.org/10.24912/jmk.v1i4.6565>
- [23]. Noegroho, O. A., Suharyono, & Kumadji, S. (2013). Pengaruh Experiential Marketing Dan *Brand Trust* Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Dan Loyalitas Pelanggan. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 6(2).
- [24]. Anggraini, F., & Budiarti, A. (2020). Pengaruh Persepsi Harga, Promosi, Dan Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Dimediasi Kepuasan Pelanggan Pada Konsumen Gojek. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi (Jupe)*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.26740/jupe.v8n3.p86-94>
- [25]. Caroline, O., & Karina, R. (2018). Pengaruh *Brand Image* Terhadap *Brand Loyalty* Melalui *Brand Satisfaction* Pada *Brand* Imaparts. *Agora*, 6(1).
- [26]. Darmanto, R. F., & Ariyanti, A. (2020). Peranan Kualitas Pelayanan, Persepsi Harga Dan Suasana Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Bakso Boedjangan Bintara. *Jurnal Pengembangan Wiraswasta*, 22(01). <https://doi.org/10.33370/jpw.v22i01.383>
- [27]. Devindiani, E., & Wibowo, L. A. (2016). Pengaruh Experiential Marketing Terhadap Customer Satisfaction Serta Dampaknya Pada Customer Loyalty (Survei Pada Pengguna Smartphone Di Komunitas Online Apple Dan Samsung Regional Bandung). *Journal Of Business Management Education (Jbme)*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.17509/jbme.v1i1.2284>
- [28]. Dharmayana, I., & Rahanatha, G. (2017). Pengaruh *Brand Equity*, *Brand Trust*, *Brand Preference*, Dan Kepuasan Konsumen Terhadap Niat Membeli Kembali. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 6(4).
- [29]. Diab, B. (2009). Analisis Pengaruh Nilai Pelanggan Dan Citra *Brand* Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Dalam Meningkatkan Retensi Pelanggan (Studi Kasus Pada Gies Batik Pekalongan). *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*.
- [30]. Dimiyati, M. (2017). Peranan Experiential Marketing Dalam Kepuasan Pasien Dalam Menciptakan Loyalitas Pasien Rumah Sakit Fatimah Banyuwangi. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*.
- [31]. Hadiwidjaja, R. S., & Dharmayanti, D. (2014). Analisa Hubungan Experiential Marketing, Kepuasan Pelanggan, Loyalitas Pelanggan Starbucks Coffee Di Surabaya Town Square. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 2(2).
- [32]. Herliza, R., & Saputri, M. E. (2016). Pengaruh *Brand Image* Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Studi Pada Zara Di Mall Pvj Bandung. *E-Proceeding Of Management*, 3(2).
- [33]. Hansemark, O. C., & Albinsson, M. (2004). Customer satisfaction and retention: the experiences of individual employees. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 14(1), 40-57.
- [34]. Jeremia, K., & Djurwati, P. (2019). Pengaruh Service Quality, *Trust*, dan Consumer Satisfaction Terhadap Consumer Loyalty Pada CV. Sarana Marine Fiberglass. *Jurnal Emba: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 7(1), 831-840.
- [35]. Kotler, Philip; Armstrong, Garry, 2008. *Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran*, Jilid 1, Erlangga, Jakarta.
- [36]. Keller, Kevin L. 2013. *Strategic Brand Management; Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity*. Fourth Edition Harlow, English: Pearson Education Inc.
- [37]. Kotler and Keller (2012). *Marketing Management*”, Global Edition, Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- [38]. Duman Kurt, S., & Atrek, B. (2012). The classification and importance of E-S-Qual quality attributes: an evaluation of online shoppers. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 22(6), 622-637.
- [39]. Zehir, C., & Narcikara, E. (2016). *E-service quality* and e-recovery service quality: effects on value perceptions and loyalty intentions. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229, 427-443.
- [40]. Warusman, J. D., & Untarini, N. (2016). Pengaruh citra *brand* dan kepercayaan *brand* terhadap loyalitas pelanggan (studi pada anggota komunitas Sepeda Motor Honda Vario 125cc di Surabaya). *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen (JIM)*, 4(2), 35-41.
- [41]. Rahayu, S., & Harsono, M. (2017, Januari). Kepercayaan *Brand* dan *Brand Affect* Sebagai Antecedent dari Loyalitas *Brand*. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis Media Ekonomi*, XVIII, 9 - 22.
- [42]. Andi, Prastowo. (2015). *Panduan Kreatif Membuat Bahan Ajar Inovatif*. Yogyakarta: Diva Press. Arief, S. Sadiman, dkk.
- [43]. Zulfikar, R. (2008). Pengaruh Bauran Ritel terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen pada Toserba X di Kota Bandung.
- [44]. Rahmawati, E. (2015). Pengaruh customer engagement terhadap kepuasan pelanggan dan kepercayaan *brand* serta dampaknya pada loyalitas *brand*. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 15(2), 246-261.